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Research Article

A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY ON ANTITHROMBIN III (AT) AS SIGN OF THICKENING OF CONNECTIVE TISSUE IN CHRONIC HEPATITIS C

¹Dr. Umme Habiba, ²Dr. Shamia Zeeshan, ³Dr. Muzammal Hussain

^{1,2} University College of Medicine & Dentistry, University of Lahore, ³ Frontier Medical and Dental College, Abbottabad.

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Abstract:

Objective: We aimed in this study to develop the part of Antithrombin III like a non-invasive sign of the thickening and scarring of connective tissue in endurable condition in which the liver does not function properly due to long-term damage known as hepatitis C.

Study design: Cross-sectional descriptive study.

Place and duration: This analysis was conducted in the Department of Hematology of Federal Post Graduate Medical Institute, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore with duration of 1 year from March 2016 to March 2017.

Methodology: This analysis consists of 50 patients of endurable hepatitis C. According to the histological phases of thickening of connective tissue these patients were more on separated in two groups. Group A and group B consists of phases of fibrosis 0 to 3 and 4 to 7 respectively. Number of 25 chronic hepatitis cases was included in both groups. Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), platelet and Antithrombin (AT) were processed to all cases.

Results: In group A and group B the Average $\pm$ SD of cases was 96.48 ± 12.13 % and 58.92 ± 22.03 respectively where the value of P was less than 0.001. Group A and group B consists of phases of fibrosis 0 to 3 and 4 to 7 respectively. Number of 25 endurable hepatitis cases was included in both groups. Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), platelet and Antithrombin (AT) were processed to all cases.

Conclusion: These outcomes presented the AT intensity which was decreased in progressive phase of fibrosis during the matching to first fibrosis phase. Confines of analysis is number of 50 patients which were sorted in this analysis which is insufficient figure to develop the antithrombin III as non-invasive signs of hepatitis C cases in people of Pakistan. The samplings were gotten and kept at temperature of 70.0 degree centigrade before analysis, the outcomes of analysis might be a little variative of the evaluation of coagulation influences of fresh samplings.

Key words: Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), antithrombin-III (AT), fibrosis, chronic hepatitis.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Umme Habiba**

University College of Medicine & Dentistry, University of Lahore,

E-mail: umme.habibah2009@gmail.com

Cell No: +923014007104

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

The main reason of long-lasting hepatitis c is frequently relative to the complicated fault in a process which causes bleeding to stop [1]. Reduced clotting influences combination cause the quantitative and quantitative white blood cells ailments, biology of unbalanced homeostasis of liver ailment, absence of usual anticoagulants [2, 3, 4]. Cirrhosis is progressed in almost 20.0 % of patients of hepatitis C that is a permanent and critical ailment classified through changing over of liver tissue to fibrotic tissue and reformative nodes which outcomes in stoppage of threshold fluence of blood detached to processing of liver activity injury [5,6]. Usual anticoagulant AT is firstly produced in liver. It is the main cause of factor IX, X, XI, XII, thrombin [7]. It almost affects plasmin, kallikrein and balanced C1 enzyme [8]. Due to improper treatments the defect of AT gets through in the last stage of liver ailment, decreased transcapillary flux proportions and prolix IV coagulation [9,10]. Endurance liver ailment in the association of hepatitis C similarly the intensity of Antithrombin is significantly decreased [11]. Because of the deficiency of reticence of AT, the patients have durable revolution of progressed effects of coagulation. The consequents of thrombus pattern are raised due to vessel wall injury, modification of blood coagulability and continuity. The liver ailments are not preserved due to the equilibrium among the anticoagulants and pro-coagulants that is vital for prevention of extra thrombin development through terms of physiology. Therefore, the increased thrombin directs the block of rotation of blood and hypoxia that is concerning with remodeling of tissue and pattern of raised clot that converts in symptoms of fibrosis [12]. The procedure in which a small needle is inserted into the liver to collect a tissue sample is a useful way to describe the processing of fibrosis in endurable hepatitis C by necro-inflammatory function which is indulged with grading and fibrosis that are often transferred to like phasing [13]. Thus, biopsy is relative to main uneasiness and complexity. It is precious and invasive also [14]. Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) enzymes of liver are raised up in the endurable liver ailments. Calculations of these enzymes is indulged in the presenting examinations of liver ailments and is a pre-sign of asymptomatic hepatic ailments. The proportion of ALT and AST is an analyst of fibrosis like a ratio greater than 1 is projected as a cirrhosis examination [15]. Thrombocytopenia is available as an extreme so the value of platelet is also an analyst of fibrosis of liver and related to the phase of fibrosis [16]. The intensity of Antithrombin (AT) of endurable liver ailment cases is evaluated through our

analysis and various phases of fibrosis are related to it. Antithrombin can be processed like noninvasive indicators of fibrosis by its progressed phase. The definition of AT intensity would be important for the description of fibrosis in endurable liver ailment according to the clinical observation [17].

METHODOLOGY:

This analysis consists of 50 patients of endurable hepatitis C. According to the histological phases of thickening and scarring of connective tissue these cases were more on separated in two groups. Group A and group B consists of phases of fibrosis 0 to 3 and 4 to 7 respectively. Numbers of 25 endurable hepatitis cases were included in both groups. Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), platelet and Antithrombin-III (AT) were processed to all cases. As per HAI the histological variation of Endurable hepatitis were categorized. The Endurable hepatitis sorting value that is 1 to 8 which references to necro-inflammatory process as the calculation of the fragmentary necrosis value which is 0 to 4, threshold irritation value which is from 0 to 4, pivotal lytic necrosis, pivotal irritation and apoptosis value which is from 0 to 4 and merging necrosis value from 0 to 6. The fibrosis value which is from 0 to 6 is associated to the level and grade of fibrosis, progress of cirrhosis and architectural modifications. The oral contraceptives cases, functional deterioration of a structure cirrhosis, inherited absence of DIC and AT and anticoagulants cases were sorted out from this analysis.

Repeated sampling technique was processed. On the day of liver surgery, the blood sample were gathered from every patient. Through the average of a 10 ml of not reusable injection was use to collect blood. Blood 3 ml was pre-transferred to EDTA vessels for platelet evaluation, 3 ml to sodium citrate 3.2 % in blood collection tube for AT-III and the remaining was referred to the yellowish upper gel blood collecting tube for Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) evaluation. Platelet value of the total samplings was calculated computerized controlled HAS XT- 1800i. Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) process intensity in an amber-colored, protein-rich liquid which separates out when blood coagulates was defined through market presence of medicine FORTRESS by processing HUM-ALYZER 3500 tester in Germany Human Diagnostics. The numerical analyses of AT according to the definition of Antithrombin process intensity in plasma through artificial chromogenic substrate procedure by processing the STA Compact auto analyzer in France by Diagnostics Stango. The

fetching of chromogenic analysis was relative to the absorption of monochromatic O.D which is 405 nm light. The plasma was reared in the availability of heparin with confined approach of thrombin. The remaining thrombin was evaluated then through its amidolytic activity of the PNA and was calculated at 405 nm. So, the value of thrombin counteracted in the primary influence step was rational to the intensity of Antithrombin available in the plasma which is examined and the 2nd step of counteracted thrombin which is evaluated as PNA statement was indefinitely rational to the intensity of Antithrombin of the examined plasma. The information was studied through SPSS version 16. Average $\pm$ SD was provided for capacity differences. The analyzation of average differences in the various groups, was processed by two sovereign sample t-test. The analysis of correlation among numerical differences was processed by PMCC. The possible two-tailed

score of less than 0.01 were suggested to be constant according to statistics.

RESULTS:

A total of 50 patients which were treated for hepatitis C with average age of 44.40 ± 6.26 years which ranges from 22 years to 52 years were analyzed in our analysis. Number of male and female patients was 27 and 23 respectively. Total of 25 endurable hepatitis cases were included in both groups. In group A and group B the Average $\pm$ SD of cases was 96.48 ± 12.13 % and 58.92 ± 22.03 respectively where the value of P was less than 0.001. Group A and group B consists of phases of fibrosis 0 to 3 and 4 to 7 respectively. ALT, AST, platelet and AT were processed to all cases. Maximum average of range was 23.0 % to 111.0 %. As the intensity of Antithrombin matched in the groups. Age and gender distribution are shown below in table no 01.

Table No 01: Age and gender distribution

	Statistics	No of Patients	Percentage
Gender	Male	27	54.0%
	Female	23	46.0%
Age	Average Age	44.40 $\pm$ 6.26(Years)	
	Age Range	22-52 (Years)	

The average score of Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) in previous fibrosis was 142.56 IU/L $\pm$ 52.47 IU/L with 84.0 to 258.0 IU/L and 118.24 ± 46.66 IU/L with range of 65.0 to 242.0 IU/L accordingly versus the progressive fibrosis 295.32 IU/L $\pm$ 89.99 IU/L with range of 92.0 to 428.0 IU/L and 245.71 ± 81.81 with range of 78.0 to 388.0 accordingly. A substantial variation where the value of P was less than 0.001 was analyzed while the average scores were matched

among the groups. Average platelet value was maximum as $254.72 \pm 71.68 \times 10^9$ /L where range was 156 to 395×10^9 /L when analyzed in fibrosis phase from 0 to 3 whereas the progressive phase of fibrosis 4 to 6 explored the suggestively minimum average platelet value of $120.88 \pm 76.4 \times 10^9$ /L with range of 38.0 to 348.0×10^9 /L. There was a substantial variation among the both groups where the value of P was less than 0.001. above given details are shown below in following tabular forms.

Table No 02: Score of Modified Staging.

Staging: Fibrosis, Cirrhosis and Architectural changes, Probable or Definite Cirrhosis	Value
Marked bridging (P-P and/or P-C) with occasional nodules (incomplete cirrhosis)	05
Fibrous expansion of portal areas with marked bridging portal to portal (P-P) as well as portal to central (P-C)	04
Fibrous expansion of most portal areas with occasional portal to portal (P-P) bridging	03
Fibrous expansion of most portal areas, with or without short fibrous septa	02
Fibrous expansion of some portal areas, with or without short fibrous septa	01
No fibrosis	00

Table no 03: Mean value of the Antithrombin III in stage 0 – 3 and 4 – 6.

Study variables	Stage (0 to 3)		Stage (4 to 6)		P-value
	Mean $\pm$ SD	Range	Mean $\pm$ SD	Range	
AT %	96.48 $\pm$ 12.13	78.0 to 117.0	58.92 $\pm$ 22.03	23.0 to 111.0	<0.001

Table no 04: Mean values of the AST and ALT in stage 0 – 3 and stage 4 – 6.

Study variables	Stage (0 to 3)		Stage (4 to 6)		P-value
	Mean $\pm$ SD	Range	Mean $\pm$ SD	Range	
AST IU/L	142.56 $\pm$ 52.47	84.0 to 258.0	295.72 $\pm$ 89.9	92.0 to 428.0	< 0.001
ALT IU/L	118.24 $\pm$ 46.66	65.0 to 242.0	245.71 $\pm$ 81.81	78.0 to 388.0	< 0.001

Anti-thrombin intensity of patients

DISCUSSION:

Cirrhosis can be observed through the biochemical examinations, analyses of fibrosis indications, analyses of radiology and permutation of clinical statistics. Liver surgery is the supreme level for the observation of cirrhosis. Thus, the operation is relative to the uneasiness of patient and consequence of main complexity having mortality. It is precious

and invasive so far. Therefore, a cheap, absolute and non-invasive procedure for the treatment of cirrhosis must be developed. Our outcomes verified the average plasma intensity of Antithrombin were instantly maximum in the Group versus Group B where the fibrosis phases were 0 to 3 and 4 to 7 respectively. In the current analysis we concluded the lowering in antithrombin intensity by progression of

fibrosis. Like in the Group A and group B the antithrombin intensity and absorption were observed as percentage of 96.48 % and 58.92 % respectively. Suggestively the minimum intensity of Antithrombin in the progressed phase of fibrosis was stated through an else analysis done by papatheodoridis et al in the year 2003 [18]. The intensity of AT-III in plasma were minimum in cases of endurable cirrhosis where value of P was less than 0.05. The non-invasive signs of cirrhosis treatment can be taken through these minimum intensities of AT-III in the cases of endurable liver ailment [19]. The decrease of AT-III in endurable liver illness like plasma reduction of AT-III is instantly decreased in cirrhosis were examined through many analysis [20,21]. The intensity of antithrombin in endurable hepatitis is decreased and might be processed as a pre-sign of hepatocellular injury was presented in the year 2012 by Saray et al [22]. In minimally invasive treatment for pelvic congestion syndrome, a painful condition resulting from the presence of enlarged or varicose veins in the pelvis there is an interruption of microcirculation of liver that directs towards the variations of plasma reduction in AT-III of Cirrhosis [23]. Phlebitis and thrombosis direct the block of tiny connective or hepatic nerves that directs progression of fibrosis and development of endurable liver ailment and finally mortality of hepatocytes. Because of insufficient hepatic combination the prolix IV coagulation and decreased transcapillary flux proportions in liver cirrhosis the intensities of Antithrombin-III are mostly minimum [24].

CONCLUSION:

Confines of analysis is number of 50 patients which were sorted in this analysis which is insufficient figure to develop the antithrombin III as non-invasive signs of hepatitis C cases in people of Pakistan. The samplings were gotten and kept at temperature of 70.0 degree centigrade before analysis, the outcomes of analysis might be a little variative of the evaluation of coagulation influences of fresh samplings. It is observed that Antithrombin III (AT) intensity was instantly decreased with progressive phases of fibrosis and it could be processed like non-invasive sign of fibrosis to endurable hepatitis C patients.

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